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Research Article

Bioinformatics Guided Antioxidant Property of Turmeric (*Curcuma Longa*)

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates turmeric's (*Curcuma longa*) antioxidant properties by identifying bioactive compounds and their interactions with genes involved in inflammation and oxidative stress. Using in vitro and in-silico methods, including network pharmacology and molecular docking, we assess interactions between turmeric compounds and key target genes like NFKB1, MAPK1, and NOS3. Phytochemical screening, solvent extraction, and DPPH assays are used to evaluate antioxidant activity. The findings aim to improve understanding of how turmeric compounds help mitigate oxidative stress, with potential applications in treating oxidative stress-related diseases.

INTRODUCTION

Bioinformatics uses techniques from computer science and statistics to manage and analyze molecular data, aiding biological research. For example, the Protein Data Bank stores 3D structures of macromolecules, facilitating data access and submission⁽¹⁾ Oxygen, known as the "Janus gas," plays a dual role in biology—critical for functions like oxidative phosphorylation to produce ATP, but also contributing to oxidative stress through reactive oxygen species (ROS). Antioxidants typically control ROS, but when their defense fails, oxidative stress can damage tissues. The term "oxidative stress" was first used

in rubber chemistry in 1956 and expanded to cellular damage in 1985.⁽²⁾ Antioxidants prevent oxidation, preserving food quality and delaying spoilage, especially in fats and oils.⁽³⁾ Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*), with curcumin as its active compound, has antiviral, anticancer, and cognitive benefits. It is widely used in medicine, cosmetics, and food, remaining nontoxic even at higher doses.⁽⁴⁾

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Active Compounds in Turmeric: Data on curcuma longa active compounds was collected from the IMPPAT database, PubMed, Google

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Scholar, and PubChem for chemical information and SMILES structure. ⁽⁵⁾

Drug Likeness Screening: MolSoft software was used to evaluate the drug likeness score based on Lipinski's Rule of Five, considering factors like lipophilicity, H-bond donors/acceptors, and molecular weight. ⁽⁶⁾

Target Prediction: SuperPred database was used to predict targets for turmeric compounds, selecting those with over 70% probability. ⁽⁷⁾

Oxidative Stress Targets: GeneCards database was queried for oxidative stress-related targets with a relevance score ≥ 5.0 . ⁽⁸⁾

Common Targets Identification: Venny and Cytoscape were used to identify and visualize common targets between curcuma longa compounds and oxidative stress-related targets. ⁽⁹⁾

Protein-Protein Interaction (PPI) Network Construction: STRING database created PPI networks for common targets, with Cytoscape used to identify core targets through network analysis. ⁽¹⁰⁾

Drug-Active Compound-Target-Pathway Network: KEGG pathways for oxidative stress-related diseases were analyzed, and corresponding targets were imported into Cytoscape to visualize the network. ⁽¹¹⁾

Molecular Docking and Biological Activity Prediction: PASS Online predicted the biological activity of compounds, comparing them with known active/inactive structures to estimate their effectiveness. ⁽¹²⁾

Protein Structure Prediction and Quality Check: PROCHECK and ERRAT were used to assess the structural quality of predicted proteins using Ramachandran plots and error statistics. ⁽¹³⁾

Protein and Ligand Preparation for Docking: Protein structures were obtained from the RCSB PDB, and ligands from PubChem, both in 3D formats, for use in docking simulations. ⁽¹⁴⁾

In-Vitro Methodology:

Plant Material: Fresh turmeric rhizomes (*Curcuma longa*) were collected from Chikkodi Taluka, Belgaum District, Karnataka, India, and authenticated by Mrs. S. B. Patil, Associate Professor, GI Bagewadi College.

Chemicals and Reagents: Analytical grade chemicals were used, including DPPH, methanol, various reagents (e.g., Mayer's, Wagner's, Hager's), and potassium hydroxide pellets, sourced from Shree Enterprises. ⁽¹⁵⁾

Preliminary Phytochemical Evaluation: The crude extract was tested for phytoconstituents like carbohydrates, proteins, alkaloids, glycosides, terpenes, steroids, flavonoids, tannins, and saponins using standard tests. ⁽¹⁵⁾

Extraction Procedure: 100g of dried turmeric rhizome was ground, and the powder was macerated with 350ml of 90% ethanol for 3 hours, followed by percolation with 150ml of ethanol for 7 days, yielding a crimson-red extract stored in a dark, cool place. ⁽¹⁶⁾

Antioxidant Activity (DPPH ASSAY):

Sample Preparation: Three extract dilutions (250 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, and 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) were prepared in ethanol.

DPPH Assay: 200 μl of extract was mixed with 1.8ml of 0.5mM DPPH ethanol solution, incubated for 30 minutes, and absorbance at 517nm was measured. Ascorbic acid was used as the standard. The inhibition percentage was calculated using the formula. ⁽¹⁷⁾

$$\% \text{ Inhibitor} = \frac{A \text{ Control} - A \text{ Sample}}{A \text{ Control}} \times 100$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

(In-Silico Network Pharmacology)

From 100 phytochemicals of *Curcuma longa* rhizomes analyzed via the IMPPAT Database, 13 compounds were selected based on drug-likeness scores from Molsoft: Thymol acetate, Bisabolone, Heptyl salicylate, Cyclocurcumin, Xanthorrhizol, 4-Carvomenthenol, 2-Hepten-4-one, Carvacrol,

Turneronol A, Gamma-Terpineol, Procurcumadiol, Sesquisabinene, and Furanodienon. Their drug-likeness scores ranged from 0.00 to 0.52. Using Venny, common targets were identified between the selected phytochemicals and disease targets were identified. Pathways linked to oxidative stress damage and phytochemical activity were also explored. These genes and targets were used to create a network using Cytoscape, highlighting the interactions between the compounds and their biological pathways.

Network Pharmacology

Network pharmacology analysis identified key phytochemicals in *Curcuma longa*, including Furandienon, Xanthorrhizol, Thymol Acetate, Procurcumadiol, Bisabolone, Carvomenthenol, Gamma Terpeneol, and Sesquisabinene. These compounds interact with target genes such as NFKB1, MAPK1, NOS3, and HSP90AA1, influencing antioxidant pathways.

Molecular Docking:

The molecular docking method is widely employed in the development of structure-based drugs. When it comes to drug discovery

investigations, docking is critical. Docking is the process of selecting the best ligand-binding configuration that is both energetically and geometrically compatible with the protein binding site. Docking procedures. Begin by selecting a protein and a ligand molecule. Get the ligand and protein ready. In Protein, choose your docking location. Use the Protein Ligand Docking Tool to complete the process. By performing molecular Docking of ligands such as Furandienon, Xanthorrhizol, Thymol Acetate, Procurcumadiol, 1 Bisabolone, 4 Carvomenthenol, Gamma Terpeneol and Sesquisabinene with target genes such as NFKB1, MAPK1, NOS3, HSP90AA1, PIK3R1, PRKCA, TLR4, PIK3CA we get binding affinities which is mentioned in Table 1

Table1: Binding affinity of Phytochemicals or ligands

Target name	HSP90 AA1	MAP K1	NFKB 1	NOS3	PIK3C A	PIK3R 1	PRKC A	TLR4
Ligand name	Affinity (kcal/mol)							
l-bisabolone	-5.1	-4.8	-3.8	-5.6	-5.4	-5.2	-5.6	-5.2
	-5.0	-4.5	-3.5	-5.3	-5.2	-4.8	-4.8	-4.8
	-4.7	-4.1	-3.1	-4.9	-4.8	-4.6	-4.3	-4.4
	-4.5	-3.9	-2.8	-4.6	-4.6	-4.2	-3.9	-4.0
	-4.2	-3.6	-2.5	-4.1	-4.2	-3.9	-3.6	-3.7
furanodienon	-6.2	-7.6	-4.8	-5.6	-7.1	-6.3	-7.2	-6.2
	-5.9	-7.4	-4.5	-5.2	-6.8	-6.0	-6.9	-5.8
	-5.4	-7.1	-4.1	-4.9	-6.5	-5.7	-6.4	-5.4
	-5.1	-6.9	-3.8	-4.6	-6.1	-5.2	-6.1	-5.0
	-4.8	-6.5	-3.4	-4.3	-5.7	-4.9	-5.8	-4.7
xanthorrhizol	-5.4	-6.5	-5.0	-5.8	-6.9	-5.7	-7.3	-5.9
	-5.2	-6.2	-4.7	-5.4	-6.4	-5.3	-6.9	-5.6
	-4.9	-5.9	-4.4	-5.0	-6.0	-4.9	-6.5	-5.2
	-4.6	-5.7	-4.0	-4.7	-5.7	-4.6	-6.2	-4.7
	-4.2	-5.2	-3.6	-4.2	-5.3	-4.2	-5.8	-4.3
Thymol acetate	-4.9	-6.2	-4.6	-5.0	-6.2	-5.3	-5.4	-5.9
	-4.5	-5.9	-4.4	-4.6	-5.8	-5.0	-5.0	-5.5
	-4.0	-5.4	-4.0	-4.1	-5.3	-4.6	-4.6	-5.1
	-3.7	-5.0	-3.6	-3.7	-5.0	-4.2	-4.2	-4.7
	-3.4	-4.7	-3.1	-3.4	-4.7	-4.0	-3.9	-4.3
procurcumadiol	-5.8	-6.9	-5.7	-5.7	-6.6	-5.9	-5.4	-6.5
	-5.5	-6.6	-5.4	-5.3	-6.2	-5.6	-5.1	-6.2
	-5.2	-6.2	-5.1	-4.9	-5.9	-5.2	-4.8	-5.7
	-4.9	-5.8	-4.8	-4.6	-5.4	-4.8	-4.3	-5.2
	-4.7	-5.4	-4.2	-4.1	-5.0	-4.2	-4.0	-4.8
4-carvomenthenol	-5.2	-5.5	-4.3	-4.9	-5.8	-5.6	-4.8	-5.0
	-5.0	-5.1	-4.0	-4.6	-5.5	-5.2	-4.2	-4.7
	-4.8	-4.8	-3.7	-4.2	-5.1	-4.8	-3.8	-4.2
	-4.4	-4.4	-3.2	-3.9	-4.8	-4.2	-3.5	-3.8
	-4.1	-4.1	-2.9	-3.6	-4.3	-3.9	-3.1	-3.4
Gamma-terpineol	-4.9	-5.5	-4.5	-6.3	-6.3	-5.2	-5.4	-4.9
sesquisabinene	-6.8	-6.6	-4.5	-5.6	-5.4	-5.5	-6.1	5.4
	-6.5	-6.4	-4.2	-5.2	-5.0	-5.2	-5.7	-5.0
	-6.2	-6.0	-3.8	-4.8	-4.8	-4.9	-5.3	-4.8
	-5.9	-5.7	-3.4	-4.2	-4.3	-4.6	-4.9	-4.4
	-5.6	-5.1	-3.0	-3.9	-4.0	-4.2	-4.5	-4.0

The maximum affinity of -7.6 kcal/mol indicates that the Furandieon bind to the MAPK target gene and shows the higher binding affinity.

Table2: Binding Affinity of Ascorbic Acid

Target name	HSP90AA 1	MAPK 1	NFKB 1	NOS3	PIK3C A	PIK3R 1	PRKC A	TLR4
Ligand name	Affinity (kcal/mol)							
Ascorbic acid	-4.8 -4.3 -3.9 -3.7 -3.3	-5.0 -4.7 -4.2 -3.8 -3.5	-4.7 -4.3 -3.8 -3.4 -3.0	-3.9 -3.5 -3.1 -2.8 -2.4	-5.5 -5.1 -4.7 -4.1 -3.7	-5.1 -4.7 -4.2 -3.9 -3.5	-5.5 -5.1 -4.7 -4.2 -3.8	-5.1 -4.7 -4.1 -3.7 -3.3

Ramachandran Plots:

Plot is produced by the PROCHECK tool using an input of a protein file that has been simulated. It shows that the most preferred regions, additional allowed regions, generously allowed regions, and

disallowed regions for the given protein are represented by residues with 90.073%, 91.257%, 91.835%, and 96.011%, respectively. No residue should be found in the banned or outlier zone, and no more than 2% of residues should be in the authorized region. It is shown in figure 1,2,3,4.

Figure 1: NOS3

Figure 2: NFKB1

Figure 3: MAPK1

Figure 4: PIK3CA

Errat:

Based on statistics of non bonded interactions between various atom types computed by its sophisticated structural database. Figures 5,6,7, and 8 depict a graph between residues and error values as the ERRAT server's output. This input

structure has a strong overall quality score of 90.073%, 91.257%, 91.835%, and 96.011%. The input structure should have a quality score of more than 95% if it has good resolution. With a resolution of 2-3, the protein structure shows a score of more than 90%. In the ERRAT graph, regions with red and yellow colour represent the

problematic part while the white colour represents the normal part in the structure. Residues with

error values more than 95% and 99% can easily be identified from the plot analysis.

Figure 5 NOS3

Figure 6 NFKB1

Figure 7 MAPK1

Figure 8 PIK3CA

Hence by comparing between Table 9 and Table 10 Crude extract of Curcuma Longa rhizomes

phytoconstituents shows Higher affinity than the Standard drug.

Interaction between furanodienon and MAPK1
MAPK1

Receptor – Ligand interaction fuannodienon

In-Vitro Studies:

Antioxidant Activity of Fruit by DPPH Assay Method:

Test sample

At every concentration tested (250µg, 500µg, 1000µg), there was a noticeable radical scavenging activity. Ethanolic extract of Curcuma Longa Rhizhome at 250 µg/ml concentration shows free radical scavenging activity with 79.43% inhibition

and at 500 µg/ml concentration shows free radical scavenging activity with 84.07% inhibition and at 1000 µg/ml concentration shows free radical scavenging activity with 89.79% inhibition.

Standard Drug: At every concentration tested (250µg,500 µg,1000 µg), there was a noticeable

radical scavenging activity. Ethanol is used as a solvent. At 250 µg/ml concentration shows radical scavenging activity with 68.84% inhibition and at 500 µg/ml concentration shows radical scavenging activity with 72.42% and at 1000 µg/ml concentration shows radical scavenging activity with 79.90%.

Concentration In µg/ml	Free radicle scavenging activity of Test sample	Free radicle scavenging activity of Standard Drug (Ascorbic acid)
250 µg/ml	79.43%	68.84%
500 µg/ml	84.07%	72.42%
1000 µg/ml	89.79%	79.90%

CONCLUSION:

This study aimed to uncover the antioxidant potential of *Curcuma longa* (turmeric) by investigating the interactions of its bioactive compounds with key target genes associated with oxidative stress and inflammation. Through a multi-faceted approach that includes network pharmacology analysis, molecular docking simulations, and the *in-vitro* DPPH assay, valuable insights into the antioxidative properties of turmeric have been revealed. In the initial phase of the research, a panel of key target genes, including NFKB1, MAPK1, NOS3, PIK3CA, PIK3R1, TLR4, PRKCA, and HSP90AA1, were identified using network pharmacology analysis conducted with Cytoscape software. PyRx software was employed for molecular docking simulations to predict and evaluate the interactions between turmeric-derived bioactive compounds and the identified key target genes. Notably, the results indicated that MAPK1 exhibited the highest affinity for these compounds, with a particular emphasis on furanodienon's interaction with this protein. To assess the antioxidant properties of the bioactive compounds, *in vitro* experiments using the 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) assay were conducted. This quantitative assay allowed

for the measurement of these compounds' ability to scavenge free radicals, and it demonstrated that the ethanolic extract of *Curcuma Longa* rhizome outperformed the industry standard antioxidant, ascorbic acid. In summary, this comprehensive research has identified specific phytoconstituents in turmeric, such as beta sesquiosabinene, gamma terpineol, 4 carvomenthenol, 1 bisabolone, procurcumadiol, thymol acetate, xanthorrhizol, and furanodienon, that interact with key target genes involved in oxidative stress and inflammation. The *in-silico* data from network pharmacology and molecular docking have provided a foundation for further validation procedures, highlighting the strong affinity of MAPK1 for turmeric-derived compounds, especially furanodienon. *In-vitro* experiments with the DPPH assay have shown that *Curcuma Longa* rhizome ethanolic extract possesses remarkable antioxidant capabilities, surpassing the performance of the industry-standard antioxidant, ascorbic acid. These combined findings significantly contribute to the understanding of how turmeric-derived bioactive compounds may effectively combat oxidative stress damage caused by free radicals. The research underscores the potential health benefits of *Curcuma longa* and emphasizes the broader implications of harnessing

natural compounds in addressing oxidative stress-related health issues. This work lays the groundwork for future investigations and the development of antioxidant interventions based on turmeric-derived compounds. Further investigation for the study required.

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